

Research Article

Performance of Malaysian Islamic Unit Trusts Based on Consistency of Ranking

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Abstract

In this study, the performance of Malaysian Islamic unit trust is investigated based on consistency of ranking and can be considered as an alternative approach in evaluating portfolio performance. The Sign Test is employed to investigate consistency of ranking. The results of this study indicate that only four unit trusts namely Public Islamic Equity and CIMB Islamic Sukuk (both for short term investment) and Public Islamic Balance and CIMB Islamic Balance (both for medium term investment) exhibit non-random behavior in ranking which implies that the two unit trusts exhibit consistency and predictability in ranking. All other unit trusts show that the consistency in ranking is random and unpredictable consistent with the efficient market hypothesis.

Key words: market efficiency, unit trust, consistency, ranking

JEL Classification: G25

1.0 Introduction

Malaysia has been recognized as a pioneer and at the forefront in Islamic finance development. Presently, Malaysia far surpasses other Muslim countries in terms of market infrastructure and human resource development with unflagging government supports in providing the impetus for growth of the local Islamic Capital Market (ICM). The ICM refers to the market where activities are carried out in ways which are shariah-compliant and does not conflict with the principles of Islam. In Malaysia, the ICM functions as a parallel market to the conventional capital market for capital seekers and providers. It has played a complementary role to the Islamic banking system in creating a comprehensive Islamic financial market in Malaysia.

The growing awareness of and demand for investing in accordance with Islamic principles on a global scale has created a flourishing world Islamic capital market (estimated to be worth at USD1 trillion), more so today due to increasing wealth in the hands of Muslims worldwide (that represents about 20-30% of world population) who are actively involved in corporate and business activities. Today, the Islamic financial market runs parallel to the conventional financial market and provides investors with an alternative investment philosophy and model that is rapidly gaining acceptance. The fact that the Islamic financial market does not prohibit participation of non-Muslims creates unlimited upside to the depth and breadth of this market.

Islamic capital market which conforms to the Shariah principle has been introduced by the Malaysian government in order to meet the increasing demand for alternative investment vehicles. In term of the Malaysian unit trust funds, the Islamic funds are relatively new as compared to the conventional funds. Unit trust funds, is important to investors because investors are motivated to ensure the maximum return on their investments. Therefore information about the efficiency of unit trust funds is one of the major considerations in the fund-selection decision (Berger et al. 1993).

Evaluating the unit trust performance is one of the important aspects that must be considered. The level of performance will somehow influence how the investors viewed the Islamic unit trust companies. In other words, satisfied investors view the company with higher the level of confidence and the tendency of them to invest in the company.

There is a lack of evidence relating to the ranking of performance of Islamic unit trust in the finance literature and this study attempts to fill the gap. Continuous efforts are being made to further improve on the techniques for evaluating the Islamic unit trust performance. Performance has been an area of frequent research. However, to the

best of the researcher's knowledge, there are not many studies that investigate the performance of unit trusts companies that is based on ranking. Most of the studies concentrated on the performance evaluation using Sharpe Index, Treynor Index and Jensen alpha besides looking at other perspectives. This study will further explore the method of performance by looking at ranking by using the sign test, the method under the nonparametric randomness method. The purpose of this study will be examined as follows;

- i. To study the performance of Islamic unit trusts using the sign test method.
 - ii. To test the randomness pattern of ranking performance in Islamic unit trusts using the sign test method.
- The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The next section (1.2) reviews prior studies on the performance of Islamic unit trusts. This is followed by section 1.3 on the research framework, the findings on section 1.4 and section 1.5 concludes the study.

1.2 Prior Studies

Empirical evidence on Islamic funds is scarce with extant studies analyzing the financial performance of less than 60 funds (Abderrezak, 2008; Abdullah et al. 2007). The longest investigation to date has been undertaken by Abdullah et al. (2007) but they used method of Jensen alpha on 14 Malaysian Islamic funds over the period 1992-2001 and found these to significantly underperform the market benchmark.

In other studies that are also focusing on Islamic unit trust performance by Elfakhani et al. (2005), they investigate 46 international Islamic funds identified by Falaika or Standard & Poors (S&P) over 68 month sample to August 2002. When they diminished the international Islamic funds on the S&P 500, the results are mainly meaningful for the portfolio of seven American funds whose alphas are insignificant. Using sensibly matched equity market benchmarks, Abderezzak (2008) re-investigated the sample of Elfakhani et al. (2005) and found only Asian domestic funds to significantly underperform. The trend is similar where most of the results underperform in the market.

Much previous literature on the performance of unit trusts did not distinguish between different classes of mutual funds. Researchers can refer a few studies and Haslem (2008) used Morningstar's distinct portfolios, so only one class of mutual fund portfolio is represented. He finds that superior performance on average occurs among large funds with low expense ratios, low trading activity and no or low front-end loads. For Tower and Zheng (2008), they ranked 51 mutual funds annually based on a study of their diversified US managed mutual funds over an 11 year period. They concluded that in the ranking aspect, it is important to compare style-adjusted performance with unadjusted performance and historical performance of the portfolios held by clients. This is in order to isolate the efficiency of managers stock picking from style picking and to assess the wisdom of individual investors.

A study by Casarin et al. (2005) also used rating measure but through Morningstar. The study stated that some private institutions recently introduced a system classification of mutual funds based on performance measure like the 'Morningstar rating' measure, and this gives rise to some questions on the relation between the relative benchmark Morningstar measure and traditional performance measures. In their study, they used a new measure which is the 'Morningstar risk-adjusted rating' proposed by Morningstar, a well-known rating company among American investors. They compare the fund's ranking produced by every risk-adjusted performance for every period, using Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient. They used nonparametric methods, cross-product ratio and chi-square test to examine the persistency and it is observed that only the Morningstar rating measure generates a strong degree of persistence.

According to the Lipper Fund website, ranking is a non-judgmental mathematical process in which like funds are arrayed on the basis of their performance. Lipper ranks fund performance universally and within their classification system. If funds have the same performance, it is the company policy to assign within the same rank.

The research by Khalid et al. (2010) in Pakistan measures the performance of 23 active closed-ended funds from 2001-2008. The ranking differentials through various measures indicate fluctuating environment of Pakistan money market. In the light of varying investment objectives, the results of different funds, causing dissimilarities in their ranking. This shows that the ranking of funds changed due to fluctuating environment of market which is not suitable for the performance of closed-ended mutual funds. There is unsatisfactory performance of these funds which shows that the industry is not at a flourishing stage in Pakistan.

In Malaysia, based on the study by Tan (1995) that investigates the investment performance and ranking of a sample of 21 unit trust funds for the period of January 1984 to December 1993, the findings revealed that the funds as a whole performed worse than the market portfolio. Their performance was quite consistent, the market risks were stable over time and held quite well diversified portfolios. Generally the funds did not adhere very well to their stated objectives and all the fund managers could not forecast security prices and failed to outperform the naïve buy and hold strategy. It was found that larger funds and funds that practice active trading were more risky, while the older funds however were more risk averse.

The findings in the previous research by Tan (1995) had been upgraded by Leong and Aw (1997). They examined the investment performance and ranking of unit trust funds in Malaysia from January 1984 to December 1996 with sample of 32 private unit trusts funds. The study used KLSE EMAS Index as two different benchmark portfolios. The findings revealed that the majority of the funds in the sample performed worse than KLCI and EMAS market portfolio. It was also found that the funds were not as diversified as the market portfolio and few fund managers had the forecasting ability to outperform the buy and hold strategy. When EMAS was used as benchmark portfolio, most funds were more closely diversified, and more funds had forecasting ability to outperform the market. However, the choice of benchmark portfolio did not have much impact on the performance ranking of the funds.

The research that is based on ranking performance of funds can be another piece of important information that can be used in the selection of fund investments. However ranking is not the only basis in making investment decision whereas the funds ability also needs to be evaluated and the level of risk that is able to be accepted. According to Koellner et al. (2005), the outcomes of an assessment of a fund's sustainability performance depend very much on the time perspective chosen.

Therefore, a combined assessment of past performance and projected future performance is the most reliable method of evaluating a fund's performance. This is because the consistency of sustainability performance over time is an important decision criterion.

In summary, previous studies do not quietly prefer the aspect of ranking evaluation in analyzing unit trust performance. There are only several studies that are using ranking but by using different types of benchmark and the results or findings are not quite satisfying in developing the performance of the funds. It can be seen that the financial performance and investment style of hundreds of Islamic mutual funds is unexplored to date. Consequently, the researcher considers the analysis of ranking to evaluate the performance of Islamic unit trust companies in Malaysia in order to develop more satisfying results as well as to improve previous research.

1.3 Research Framework

This study focuses on the factor of ranking that will be evaluated using the sign test method to determine the performance of Islamic unit trust companies in Malaysia. The development of the research framework is based on the randomness possibility in the ranking factor that is able to influence the performance level of Islamic unit trust companies.

In the statistical literature, a truly random process refers to a process that can produce independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) samples. Here, the randomness really equals to the i.i.d (Wang, 2003). If an observed value in the sequence is influenced by its position in the sequence, or by the observations which proceed it, the process is not truly random. The research hypotheses, where H_0 is a null hypothesis to be tested and H_1 is an alternate hypothesis for this study are as follows:

- H_0 : There is no difference in ranking performance.
 H_1 : There is a difference in ranking performance.

The null hypothesis is considered to be the most plausible scenario that can explain a set of data. The most common null hypothesis is that the data is completely random and there is no relationship between two system results. The null hypothesis is always assumed to be true unless proven otherwise. The alternative hypothesis predicts the opposite of the null hypothesis and it is said to be true if the null hypothesis is proven to be false. Investigations of randomness of a given sequence often require statistical tools for comparison of distribution. Among them, the goodness-of-fit tests and entropy estimates are two well-understood concepts (Wegenkittl, 2001).

However, when the distribution of the observed data is unknown, the hypotheses are simply like the above hypotheses. Regarding the hypotheses, nonparametric tests need to be resorted using the sign test method. In this study, the test of randomness based on runs in the ranking performance will be evaluated.

1.3.1 The Sign Test

Sprenst (1993) stated that we seldom deal with strictly random samples from a clearly specified population. More commonly it may be reasonable to assume observations represent a sample with the essential properties of a random sample from a vaguely-specified population. The sign test is like most tests where the larger the sample the greater the power and the shorter the confidence interval for a given confidence interval. The tests of randomness are designed to investigate sequences of observations and attempt to identify any deviations from randomness. Theoretical tests are necessary and useful for testing global randomness. An example of the common empirical test

Z scores or also known as 'standard scores' represent a 'standard distribution' of values about a mean of zero. The transformation of z-score is useful to compare the relative standings of items from distributions with different means or different standard deviations. It can be classified as a measure of the divergence of an individual experimental result from the most probable result, the mean. Z-scores normalize the sampling distribution for meaningful comparison and it requires independent random data. In this study, the z-score is based on the results from the expected run and the variance of run (R). The standard deviation is the unit measurement of the z-score. It allows comparison of observations from different normal distributions, which is done frequently in research. The use of 'Z' is because the normal distribution is also known as the 'Z distribution'. They are most frequently used to compare a sample to a standard normal deviate, though they can be defined without assumptions of normality. The z-score will serve as statistical criteria for the rejection of H_0 . The z-score standardize scores and compare raw scores from different bunches of data.

1.4 Main findings

(i) Bond Fund

The findings for three months, six months, one year, three years and five years for bond fund are summarized in Table 1.4.1a through 1.4.1e.

Table 1.4.1a: Three Months Analysis of Islamic Bond Fund

Bond	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Sukuk	-1.414	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Bond	0.267	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Bond	1.203	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL As-Saad	-0.303	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Bon Isl.	-1.416	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.1b: Six Months Analysis of Islamic Bond Fund

Bond	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Sukuk	-2.423	± 1.96	Reject H_0
RHB Isl.Bond	-0.092	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Bond	1.122	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL As-Saad	-0.102	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Bon Isl.	-0.985	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.1c: One Year Analysis of Islamic Bond Fund

Bond	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Sukuk	0.042	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Bond	-0.299	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Bond	0.215	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL As-Saad	0.263	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Bon Isl.	-0.131	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.1d: Three Years Analysis of Islamic Bond Fund

Bond	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Sukuk	-0.174	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Bond	-0.047	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Bond	-1.296	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL As-Saad	-0.252	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Bon Isl.	-0.467	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.1e: Five Years Analysis of Islamic Bond Fund

Bond	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Sukuk	0.542	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Bond	0.349	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL As-Saad	0.370	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Bon Isl.	0.370	± 1.96	Accept H_0

It can be concluded that most of the Islamic unit trust funds behavior are random. Only one result rejects the null hypothesis. There is a difference in the ranking of Islamic unit trust performance by the CIMB Islamic Sukuk in the six months period as seen in Table 1.4.1b. So it can be concluded that in this bond fund, only CIMB Islamic Sukuk have non-random ranking which means that the ranking is quite consistent all the time. The movement of ranking for CIMB Islamic Sukuk in the five years period only includes the ranking of eight, nine and ten in the 33 weeks of ranking when data are taken. Other Islamic unit trusts exhibit random ranking and shows inconsistent pattern.

(ii) Equity Fund

The findings for three months, six months, one year, three years and five years for equity funds are summarised in Table 1.4.2a through 1.4.2e.

Table 1.4.2a: Three Months Analysis of Islamic Equity Fund

Equity	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Dali Eqty	-1.765	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Growth	-0.693	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Equity	2.079	± 1.96	Reject H_0
MAAKL Al-Fauzan	-0.475	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Equity Isl.	-1.570	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.2b: Six Months Analysis of Islamic Equity Fund

Equity	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Dali Eqty	-0.435	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Growth	0.839	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Equity	0.668	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL Al-Fauzan	0.674	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Equity Isl.	-1.237	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.2c: One Year Analysis of Islamic Equity Fund

Equity	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Dali Eqty	-0.793	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Growth	0.278	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Equity	0.136	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL Al-Fauzan	0.268	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Equity Isl.	0.205	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.2d: Three Years Analysis of Islamic Equity Fund

Equity	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Dali Eqty	0.488	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Growth	-0.826	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Equity	1.172	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL Al-Fauzan	1.416	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Equity Isl.	0.377	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.2e: Five Years Analysis of Islamic Equity Fund

Equity	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Dali Eqty	-0.128	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Isl.Growth	-0.076	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Equity	0.022	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Equity Isl.	0.030	± 1.96	Accept H_0

In terms of equity fund that can be seen from the Table 1.4.2a till Table 1.4.2e, the result is quite similar with the bond fund. Most of the Islamic unit trust companies accept the null hypothesis which means that there is random pattern in the ranking. Looking at the three months period, Public Islamic Equity is the only Islamic unit trust that rejects the null hypothesis showing that it has non-random pattern in the ranking. It can be seen that the period of six months and onwards show all data as having no relationship in ranking. This clearly shows that almost all the Islamic unit trust funds have random pattern of ranking in the short-term, medium-term and long-term period except for Public Islamic Equity.

(iii) Mixed-Asset Fund

The findings for three months, six months, one year, three years and five years for mixed-asset fund are tabulated below.

Table 1.4.3a: Three Months Analysis of Islamic Mixed-Asset Fund

Mixed-Asset	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Balance	1.719	± 1.96	Accept H_0
RHB Mudharabah	-0.943	± 1.96	Accept H_0
Public Isl.Balance	1.385	± 1.96	Accept H_0
MAAKL Al-Umran	1.203	± 1.96	Accept H_0
ING Shariah Balance	0.761	± 1.96	Accept H_0

Table 1.4.3b: Six Months Analysis of Islamic Mixed-Asset Fund

Mixed-Asset	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Balance	-0.897	±1.96	Accept H ₀
RHB Mudharabah	1.440	±1.96	Accept H ₀
Public Isl.Balance	0.090	±1.96	Accept H ₀
MAAKL Al-Umran	0.082	±1.96	Accept H ₀
ING Shariah Balance	0.102	±1.96	Accept H ₀

Table 1.4.3c: One Year Analysis of Islamic Mixed-Asset Fund

Mixed-Asset	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Balance	0.026	±1.96	Accept H ₀
RHB Mudharabah	-0.557	±1.96	Accept H ₀
Public Isl.Balance	-0.047	±1.96	Accept H ₀
MAAKL Al-Umran	0.205	±1.96	Accept H ₀
ING Shariah Balance	-0.084	±1.96	Accept H ₀

Table 1.4.3d: Three Years Analysis of Islamic Mixed-Asset Fund

Mixed-Asset	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Balance	0.742	±1.96	Accept H ₀
RHB Mudharabah	0.951	±1.96	Accept H ₀
Public Isl.Balance	2.584	±1.96	Reject H ₀
MAAKL Al-Umran	-1.668	±1.96	Accept H ₀
ING Shariah Balance	0.222	±1.96	Accept H ₀

Table 1.4.3e: Five Years Analysis of Islamic Mixed-Asset Fund

Mixed-Asset	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl.Balance	-2.188	±1.96	Reject H ₀
RHB Mudharabah	-1.286	±1.96	Accept H ₀
ING Shariah Balance	-1.536	±1.96	Accept H ₀

The results from Table 1.4.3a till Table 1.4.3e show the Islamic unit trusts under the mixed-asset fund. The three months, six months and one year show that all the Islamic unit trust funds exhibit random pattern which means that most of their performance cannot be easily tracked. In the three year period, only Public Islamic Balance rejects the null hypothesis which means that the Islamic unit trust contains non-random ranking and the pattern can be easily estimated. In the five years period, CIMB Islamic Balance rejects the null hypothesis. Mixed-asset fund, Public Islamic Balance and CIMB Islamic Balance signify non-random pattern of ranking and the ranking is always consistent and able to predict.

(iv) Money Market Fund

The findings for three months, six months, one year, three years and five years for money market fund are as follow:

Table 1.4.4a: Three Months Analysis of Islamic Money Market Fund

Money Market	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl. M.Market	0.832	±1.96	Accept H ₀
RHB Isl. Cash Mgt	0.438	±1.96	Accept H ₀
Public Isl. M.Market	0.271	±1.96	Accept H ₀
MAAKL Al-Makmun	-0.834	±1.96	Accept H ₀
ING i-Enhanced Cash	-0.588	±1.96	Accept H ₀

Table 1.4.4b: Six Months Analysis of Islamic Money Market Fund

Money Market	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl. M.Market	-0.707	±1.96	Accept H ₀
RHB Isl. Cash Mgt	0.832	±1.96	Accept H ₀
Public Isl. M.Market	-0.691	±1.96	Accept H ₀
MAAKL Al-Makmun	-0.640	±1.96	Accept H ₀
ING i-Enhanced Cash	0.061	±1.96	Accept H ₀

Table 1.4.4c: One Year Analysis of Islamic Money Market Fund

Money Market	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
CIMB Isl. M.Market	-0.410	±1.96	Accept H ₀
RHB Isl. Cash Mgt	-0.590	±1.96	Accept H ₀
Public Isl. M.Market	0.285	±1.96	Accept H ₀
MAAKL Al-Makmun	-0.684	±1.96	Accept H ₀
ING i-Enhanced Cash	-1.362	±1.96	Accept H ₀

Table 1.4.4d: Three Years Analysis of Islamic Money Market Fund

Money Market	Z-score	Critical value	Relationship
MAAKL Al-Makmun	0.399	±1.96	Accept H ₀

Money market fund results for the five Islamic unit trust companies can be seen in Table 1.4.4a until Table 1.4.4d. All Islamic unit trusts for three months until one year period signifies random ranking by accepting the null hypothesis, after that period only MAAKL Al-Makmun shows non-random pattern of ranking. This proves that performance of Islamic unit trusts in money market fund can be performed only in the short-term even though all of the Islamic unit trusts signify inconsistent ranking. This is supported by the characteristic of the money market fund itself that involve short-term portfolio and focus on low-risk and low-return investment. So it is not surprising if in the five year period, the z-score cannot be calculated and there is no relationship that can be concluded due to the no ranking data in the length of period.

1.5 Conclusion

The conclusion for this finding is that difference or no difference in the ranking is a relevant factor influencing the performance of Islamic unit trusts. As have been discussed above, most of the Islamic unit trust funds that have been put in specific type of fund (bond, equity, mixed-asset and money market) accept the null hypothesis. There is no difference in ranking of their performance means that most of them perform inconsistent ranking data. By comparing the three phases of short-term, medium-term and long-term, the flow of the ranking can be seen clearly and the performance of the Islamic unit trusts can also be evaluated.

Based on the four types of fund discussed above, it can be seen that only several Islamic unit trust companies have difference in their ranking or non-random pattern of ranking. In the short term period, non-random ranking is seen for Public Islamic Equity and CIMB Islamic Sukuk. In the medium term or one year period, all the Islamic unit trust companies show random ranking while for the long term period, the non-random ranking is seen for Public Islamic Balance and CIMB Islamic Balance. This means that only two Islamic unit trust companies, Public Bank and CIMB Group exhibit consistency in ranking. Investors are able to use ranking as one of the measures in evaluating their performance. It means that if the unit trust companies have consistency in ranking, the pattern can be easily predicted. Based on this finding, investors have limited choice of choosing Islamic unit trust and they are not able to predict the performance effectively.

This due to the finding that shows only two Islamic unit trusts companies, CIMB Group and Public Mutual Bhd, contain non-random ranking pattern of data. CIMB Islamic Sukuk and CIMB Islamic Balance, and Public Islamic Equity and Public Islamic Balance contain random ranking pattern of data. Investors need to be very selective of Islamic unit trusts that contain random and inconsistent ranking because the performance cannot be predicted easily and it depends on luck or fate. Sometimes investors are able to get satisfactory return and sometimes they will get loss. This will give advantages for investors to predict any Islamic unit trusts that they interested in even though the choice of non-random funds is limited. It can be valuable information that can be used in the selection of investment funds.

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